

INCOME AND PROFIT IN THE ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

Kenzhaev M.G.

TDIU, PhD., Associate Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20354332>

Abstract: In today's era, the concepts of income of commercial banks, the formation of bank financial results, its calculation, effective analysis, and the concepts of bank profit are not fully studied, which means that this topic is relevant. The basis for ensuring the financial stability of commercial banks is its capital and the level of profitability of banking activities. In the market economy, the goal of every commercial bank is to maximize profit as a result of optimization, increasing its income and reducing its costs. The financial indicators of banks are determined through the report on the financial results, which represents the income and expenses, and the results are evaluated. We used this bank report to determine the income and expenses of commercial banks, studied the reasonable analysis of the data on their profitability level and profit, and recommended relevant proposals.

Key words: financial stability, profitability. income, expenses, bank profit, profit, lending, interest income, interest expense, operating expense, non-interest income, non-interest expense, modernization, banking and financial system, financial results, capital, capital adequacy, capitalization of banks.

Introduction

Today, ensuring the stability of the banking and financial system of our republic is one of the most important priority tasks. The expansion and development of the banking system largely depends on increasing the level of profitability in the activities of banks and the effective use of income. This requires paying special attention to improving the credit system and increasing its volume, restoring and expanding the priority areas of structural changes in the economy, modernizing production, and technical and technological innovation.

In order to strengthen their position in the market infrastructure as a result of the effective implementation of their tasks in the economy, commercial banks are required to fully implement their functions, which, in turn, ensures the financial stability of banks. The primary necessary condition for ensuring the financial stability of commercial banks is to ensure capital adequacy, ensure the achievement of a stable level of profitability of bank assets, and pursue a policy aimed at increasing bank profits and, as a result, reducing bank expenses. Thus, income and its significance in the activities of commercial banks are important factors in ensuring the stability of the banking and financial system of our republic.

The basis for ensuring the financial stability of a bank is its capital and the level of profitability of banking activities. In a market economy, the goal of each commercial bank is to obtain high or maximum profit by increasing its income and reducing and optimizing its expenses.

In the practice of the banking system, commercial banks form their income and incur expenses in accordance with the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Central Bank of

the Republic of Uzbekistan”, “On Banks and Banking Activities”, as well as regulatory documents adopted by the Central Bank.

The relevance of its application is determined by the fact that the methodological aspects of organizing income and expense accounting in commercial banks based on international standards have not been sufficiently studied, and the existence of problems such as the formation of commercial banks' income, bank financial results, their calculation, effective analysis and distribution of bank profits.

If we pay attention to the income of commercial banks, we will see that their income consists of all received interest, commission fees and dividends. Generally, it consists of interest and non-interest income.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy, it is important to strengthen the stability of the banking and financial system and improve its quality. As part of the bank's financial results, the increase in the amount of income and the optimization of expenses provide an opportunity to strengthen the stability of the bank's activity and to form it at a high level of quality. Such an end is important in the economy.

Review of literature on the subject.

Researched by foreign and domestic economists regarding the methodological and practical foundations of strengthening the income base of commercial banks, relevant scientific conclusions and practical recommendations were made.

In his scientific views, I. Fisher showed that the traditional profit calculated by the accountant has no economic meaning, and came to the conclusion that the sale of goods actually depends on its value, the income that it brings or can bring, and recognized the financial result (profit) as an increase in value due to changes in the profitability of assets during the reporting period. According to the economist-scientist Ya.V. Sokolov, the financial result is one of the complex categories, defining it as profit or loss received during a certain reporting period. The financial result shows the change in the value of capital during the reporting period. If it increases, we talk about profit, if it decreases, we talk about loss.

According to V. Usoskin, bank management is inclined to take risks in order to obtain the highest profit, which is contrary to the interests of bank depositors.

One of the economists of our republic. Y.A. Makhmudalieva notes in her scientific research that “profit is the part of the amount of income exceeding the expenses incurred”.

Also, N.F. Karimov defined profit as an economic category and showed that it is an integral part of production relations associated with the production and distribution of part of the additional product and is manifested as part of the newly created value. That is, he recognized profit not as an accounting value, but as an economic value.

In general, based on the opinions of scientists, we understand the financial result as the difference between income and expenses, which is in the form of profit or loss.

From the above considerations, it can be seen that there is no single understanding of the formation of bank income and profit, since it depends on the goals of interested parties. These individuals must first decide what to include in the assets and how accounting profit will be calculated.

Research methodology.

Operational guidelines and statistical data of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In accordance with the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, No. PF-5992 dated May 12, 2020 “On the Strategy for Reforming the Banking System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025” and No. PF-5177 dated September 2, 2017 “On Priority Measures to Liberalize Currency Policy”, Resolutions No. PP-3620 dated March 23, 2018 “On Additional Measures to Increase the Accessibility of Banking Services” and No. PP-3270 dated September 12, 2017 “On Measures to Further Develop and Increase the Stability of the Banking System of the Republic”, as well as other regulatory legal acts in this area, the activities of commercial banks are expected to increase and research methods such as induction, deduction, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, synthesis, analysis were used in the analysis of information about their importance.

Analysis and discussion of results.

According to the recommendations of experts in world banking practice, the share of interest income in the total volume of gross income of commercial banks should be at least 70 percent. A high and stable share of interest income from loans in the total volume of interest income of commercial banks is one of the main conditions for ensuring their financial stability.

The regulatory and legal basis for the formation of the income base of commercial banks is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Banks and Banking Activities”, “On Currency Regulation”, relevant Resolutions and Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, operational instructions and statistical data of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The main goal of commercial banks is to obtain high income based on high profitability or minimizing risk. An increase in the level of income reflects the quality of bank management and determines its place in the banking system.

Financial indicators of commercial banks are determined and evaluated through their financial results report, which includes income and expenses. The report reflecting the financial status of the bank is also a report on financial results presented for the respective periods.

Table 1.

**Information on income and expenses and net profit of commercial banks in the banking system of the republic.
(in billions of soums)¹.**

¹Ўзбекистон Республикаси Марказий банкнинг интернет сайти маълумотлари 2025 йил.. асосида тайёрланган.

No. Indicators	01.04.2022 y.	01.04.2023 y.	01.04.2024 y.	01.04.2025 y.
1. Interest income	14285,0	18 833	25 872	28 898
2. Interest expenses	8740,3	12 258	18 027	20 079
3. Percentage margin (1-2)	5544,7	6 575	7 845	8 819
4. Non-interest income	8393,3	11 742	12 988	16 580
5. Interest-free expenses	2228,0	2 328	3 693	5 033
6. Operating expenses	2756,0	3 891	4 760	6 123
7. Non-interest income (loss) (4-5-6)	3410,0	5 523	4 534	5 424
8. Assessment of possible losses on credit and leasing	5591,0	6 665	7 503	8 330
9. Assessment of possible losses on other assets	807,0	1 578	1 848	1 821
10. Net profit (loss) before tax (3+7)-(8+9)	2557,0	3855,0	3 029	4 091
11. Profit tax payment expenses	660,0	789,0	648	672
12. Net profit (loss).	1897,0	3066,0	2 381	3 419

Data on income and expenses and net profit of commercial banks in the banking system of the republic are summarized in Table 1, which summarizes the results of the financial statements of banks, which reflect their income and expenses, and the amounts of interest margin, non-interest income (loss), net profit (loss) and net profit (loss) before tax are determined by performing appropriate mathematical operations. If we pay attention to the determined indicators, we can see results in the direction of growth or increase in numbers in all of them. Thus, we can see that the amount of income and net profit of commercial banks in our republic has increased during 2022-2025. The data on banking practice presented in the table confirms our opinion. Based on the results of the financial statements of banks, which reflect their income and expenses, presented in the table, we determine the coefficients of profitability indicators of commercial banks in the banking system of the republic in Table 2.

Table 2

Profitability indicators of commercial banks in the republican banking system ².

№ Indicators	01.04.2022 y.	01.04.2023 y.	01.04.2024 y.	01.04.2025 y.
1. The ratio of net profit before tax to total assets (ROA).	2,3	2,8	1,8	2,1
2. The ratio of net profit to total equity (ROE).	10,6	15,1	9,6	11,6

² The data on the website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan was prepared based on 2025.

3. The ratio of net interest income to total assets	4,9	4,7	4,7	4,4
4. The ratio of net interest income received on loans to total loan deposits.	6,5	6,4	6,6	6,4
5. The ratio of net interest income to total liabilities.	5,9	5,5	5,6	5,2
6. The ratio of net interest margin to total assets.	5,0	4,7	4,8	4,5

The profitability indicators of commercial banks in the banking system of our republic are presented in Table 2. In general, no significant changes have been observed in the results of the coefficients on the profitability indicators of banks over the years.

The total net profit of banks in 2025 amounted to 15.01 trillion soums. This indicator indicates a twofold increase compared to 2024, or rather, by 122.5%. For information, in 2024, banks received a net profit of 6.96 trillion soums. This is a very positive or high indicator, which is of great importance for the expansion and development of banking activities in the future.

The TOP-5 commercial banks that achieved the highest net profit indicators at the end of 2025 were identified.

In 2025, the banking system of Uzbekistan received a record amount of net profit - a total of 15.5 trillion soums. The highest financial results were achieved by Uzmilliybank, SQB, and Kapitalbank. At the same time, MK Bank, BRB, and Ipotekabank, which had suffered significant losses in 2024, returned to profit in 2025, while TBC Bank's net profit decreased significantly, almost to zero.

Table-3.

TOP-5 commercial banks with the highest net profit at the end of 2025³.

No	Names of commercial banks	It increased its net profit by 1 trillion soums
1.	Uzmilliybank	1.92 trillion soums
2.	Uzsanoatqurilishbank	1.88 trillion soums
3.	Kapitalbank	1.79 trillion soums
4.	Hamkorbank	1.7 trillion soums
5.	Orient Finance Bank	1.04 trillion soums

In 2025, the banking system of Uzbekistan received a record net profit of 15.5 trillion soums. The highest financial results were achieved by Uzmilliybank, SQB and Kapitalbank. At the same time, MK Bank, BRB and Ipotekabank, which suffered significant losses in 2024, returned to profit in 2025, while TBC Bank's net profit decreased significantly and almost reached zero.

³Bankers.uz оператив маълумотлари 2025 йил..

The total net profit of commercial banks at the end of 2025 has a tendency to grow. This is due to the increase in income in their activities and, as a result, the increase in the amount of profit. This situation is positive and will ensure the development of banking activities in the future.

Conclusions and suggestions

We consider it appropriate to make the following suggestions and recommendations as a conclusion, in accordance with the results of the analytical study of the income base of commercial banks based on theoretical and practical data:

- We need to ensure the proportionality between the bank's interest income from loans and interest expenses on deposits;
- When establishing commercial banks, it is advisable to form the authorized capital in a larger amount than that established by the Central Bank. This, in turn, creates an opportunity to increase bank income. Much attention is paid to this in the banking practice of developed countries.
- To ensure the effective use of the existing resource base in banking activities, it is necessary to develop and implement appropriate measures by bank monitoring;
- It is advisable for the bank to pay great attention to term deposits, which are considered cheap when attracting resources, since the cost of loans from other banks is considered expensive.

List of used literature:

1. Law No. ZURQ-580 "On Banks and Banking Activities", 05.11.2019.
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and the People of Uzbekistan, 26.12.2025.
3. Regulation No. 2696 "On the Procedure for Classification of Asset Quality in Commercial Banks and Formation of Reserves to Cover Possible Losses on Assets and Their Use", 14.07.2015.
4. REGULATION of the Board of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Procedure for Calculating Interest in Commercial Banks" dated August 23, 2023 (registered on September 29, 2023, registration number 3460).
5. Lavrushin O.I. Development of the Banking Sector and Its Infrastructure in the Economy of Russia. – M.: KNORUS, 2017. – P. 74.
6. www.bankir.ru - (News website on the banking system of Uzbekistan).
7. www.finance.uz - (Business website of the Republic of Uzbekistan).
- 8.MJ Temirkhanova. Global green economy: is one of the pressing problems in the countries of the world today for making the ecological stability. Экономика и социум, 438-44, 2024
- 9.MJ Temirkhanova. THE PRESSING PROBLEMS IN THE WORLD TODAY FOR MAKING THE ECOLOGICAL STABILITY. Экономика и социум, 442-446, 2024
- 10.МЖ Темирханова. Сравнительный анализ международной и национальной практики учета выручки. Экономика и социум, 846-851, 2024